

Contradiction

Tawhidul Islam

English Language & Literature

University of Creative Technology Chittagong, Bangladesh

Do those lives matter, indeed?
The child who isn't even aware—
What was their fault, being born in Gaza?
But we know there is a UN for Human Rights!

Weeping shakes the world,
But not their hearts. Maybe—
It's twenty thousand and one hertz!
O blind world of humanity, Rafah is no more!

Water, food, and goods—
Empty stoves burn through time.
Stones hanging from the belly,
Still, the strongest minds in the world.